

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Том 1, Выпуск 4, 31 Декабря

LEARNING THE FUNDAMENTALS OF ANTISEPTIC AND ASEPTIC

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ANNOTATION

Infection is still one of the most frequent causes of morbidity and mortality following surgery. In the era of multi-resistant organisms it is essential that all surgeons have a clear understanding of the techniques used to prevent surgical infections. This article outlines the factors which contribute to infections in surgical practice and details of some of the techniques employed to decrease their incidence.

Antiseptic and aseptic techniques play a key role in the reduction of surgical infection. Patient, surgeon and environmental factors all contribute to surgical-site infections (SSIs).

Key words: antisepsis; aseptic technique; skin preps; surgical site infections.

INTRODUCTION

The terms antisepsis and asepsis are used widely but misunderstood frequently. Antisepsis derived from the Greek “against putrefaction” and its use in modern medicine is most frequently linked to the work of Lister. It refers to the use of solutions for disinfection. Asepsis is defined as the absence of infectious organisms. Aseptic techniques are those aimed at the elimination of all infectious micro-organisms during procedures.

In addition to using standard precautions and transmission-based precautions, aseptic technique (also called medical asepsis) is the purposeful reduction of pathogens to prevent the transfer of microorganisms from one person or object to another during a medical procedure. For example, a nurse administering parenteral medication or performing urinary catheterization uses aseptic technique. When performed properly, aseptic technique prevents contamination and transfer of pathogens to the patient from caregiver hands, surfaces, and equipment during routine care or procedures. The word “aseptic” literally means an absence of disease-

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causing microbes and pathogens. In the clinical setting, aseptic technique refers to the purposeful prevention of microbe contamination from one person or object to another. These potentially infectious, microscopic organisms can be present in the environment, on an instrument, in liquids, on skin surfaces, or within a wound.

There is often misunderstanding between the terms aseptic technique and sterile technique in the health care setting. Both asepsis and sterility are closely related, and the shared concept between the two terms is removal of harmful microorganisms that can cause infection. In the most simplistic terms, asepsis is creating a protective barrier from pathogens, whereas sterile technique is a purposeful attack on microorganisms. Sterile technique (also called surgical asepsis) seeks to eliminate every potential microorganism in and around a sterile field while also maintaining objects as free from microorganisms as possible. It is the standard of care for surgical procedures, invasive wound management, and central line care. Sterile technique requires a combination of meticulous hand washing, creation of a sterile field, using long-lasting antimicrobial cleansing agents such as betadine, donning sterile gloves, and using sterile devices and instruments.

Aseptic technique at home. While your home isn't likely a surgery center, there may be a time when you or a loved one need aseptic technique. For example, you may need to change a dressing on a wound, and that requires a sterile dressing.

Note: Proper aseptic techniques require training. Before you need to change the dressing at home, a healthcare specialist should demonstrate the techniques and have you practice them. To change a sterile dressing, a person needs sterile gloves and a special dressing change kit or supplies.

Aseptic technique benefits. Whenever your skin is opened, you're vulnerable to infection. That's why it's critical for you to get prompt treatment for burns and wounds. Even intentional cuts during surgery put you at risk for infection. The way healthcare providers use aseptic techniques before, during, and after your procedure help protect you from infection.

When you need surgery or other procedures that require aseptic technique, you're already vulnerable to infections. You need your immune system to be at its strongest to heal. You have a better chance of a recovery if you don't have to fight off an infection.

Aseptic technique complications. Healthcare workers try to minimize several common kinds of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) by using aseptic techniques. These include:

- CAUTIs (pronounced caught-EASE)

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- central line-associated bloodstream infections (CLABSIs, pronounced clab-SEES)
- surgical site infections

Each of these infections represents a major healthcare concern. Medical facilities are required to report their infection rates to the federal government. If their rates are too high, the facility can face disciplinary action.

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